

Plasma etching for fabrication of complex nanophotonic lasers from bonded InP semiconductor layers

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ABSTRACT

Integrating optically active III-V materials on silicon/insulator platforms is one potential path towards improving the energy efficiency and performance of modern computing. Here we demonstrate the applicability of direct wafer bonding combined with plasma etching to the fabrication of complex nanophotonic systems out of InP layers. We explore and optimise the plasma etching of InP, validating existing processes and developing improved ones. We explore the use of microdisk lasing as a way to evaluate fabrication fidelity, and demonstrate that we can create complex lasing systems of interest to us: coupled disk cavities and random network lasers.

1. Introduction

Nanolaser systems from III-V semiconductor materials can show efficient lasing [1–5] and are promising as part of on-chip nanophotonic systems. Potential applications of these systems include controllable on-chip light sources, sensing, and physical layers for machine learning processes. As the development of smaller and more efficient compute components slows down [6,7], and the size of machine learning workloads increases, III-V photonic semiconductor systems for interconnects and computation could be a part of potential solutions for a faster and more sustainable future of computing.

In this work we are specifically interested in the fabrication and study of two kinds of nanophotonic systems: coupled microdisk lasers and random lasing networks [8]. Microdisk lasers are micron-scale disk cavities that support whispering gallery modes. When two such cavities are in close vicinity of each other, their modes can evanescently couple forming new, hybridised modes. The other system, random lasing networks, are representations of graphs realized through interconnected waveguides. Each of the graph's edges is a waveguide and the guided light scatters at the graph's nodes, where the waveguides connect. Through multiple scattering at these nodes, the networks can support random, highly multimode lasing [8,9]. Both of these systems are sensitive to tuning through selective pumping [10–12]. Their nonlinear

behaviour also shows promise for applications in physical acceleration of machine learning [13,14].

Integrating III-V on Si platforms has traditionally been difficult due to lattice and thermal mismatch. In recent years, progress in on-chip fabrication was made and III-Vs can now be integrated using multiple different techniques. Typical bottom-up techniques include aspect ratio trapping [15], nanowire growth [16], and template-assisted epitaxy (TASE) [17]. These methods have advantages: for example, directed metalorganic chemical vapour deposition (MOCVD) growth results in single-crystalline structures with extremely smooth and vertical sidewalls [17,18]. This is important for lasing devices as smoother sidewalls decrease scattering losses, and vertical walls allow for efficient evanescent coupling. However, these techniques are time-consuming and challenging for complex shapes like the networks, and the design reproducibility is poor.

A typical top-down approach is using direct wafer bonding (DWB) followed by plasma etching. In DWB a layer of III-V semiconductor (in our case Indium Phosphide, InP) is grown separately on a sacrificial wafer, and then bonded to a Si wafer through a spacer layer of SiO₂ [19]. The active layer is then etched down, yielding the desired structures. This allows for simultaneous fabrication of multiple complex designs such as coupled laser arrays, hyperuniform networks, and random lasers. DWB followed by etching also enables a higher degree of control

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and reproducibility than previous methods. The top-down approach comes with its own challenges too: etching III-V material can be complex, narrow trenches in between coupled devices demand vertical side-walls, and the networks need good-quality waveguides to limit losses as light propagates over large distances.

Here we investigate and optimise the InP etching process for use as part of the DWB approach. We then validate the application of this process to the nanophotonic devices of interest, and compare the results with those obtained using previous fabrication methods.

2. Methods

2.1. Direct wafer bonding

Wafer bonding is a way to fabricate a photonic layer with optical isolation on top of a Si wafer, avoiding the lattice mismatch defects that would arise if a III-V layer was to be directly grown on Si or insulator. It achieves this by growing the active III-V layer on a lattice-matched III-V substrate with an etch stop layer in between. This is then turned upside down and bonded to a prepared Si wafer through a buffer layer of SiO₂ and annealing [19,20]. The buried oxide (BOX) layer also isolates the III-V from the Si, leading to good optical confinement in the active layer. The sacrificial III-V wafer can then be removed by wet etching, leaving the active layer attached to the Si wafer and ready for patterning and dry etching. Here we have used InP active layers, but since the active layer is grown through MOCVD, more complex make-up is also possible, such as using layers of InP with embedded InGaAs quantum well layers.

2.2. Patterning

Chip patterning was done with optical and electron beam (e-beam) lithography. For etch test samples we initially used an optical lithography process. We first deposited a 100 nm layer of SiO₂ on the wafer using plasma-enhanced chemical vapour deposition (PECVD), then spin-coated it with 500 nm of optical resist. After exposure on a mask aligner and development, the SiO₂ layer was etched using a RIE tool to form the hard mask. The optical resist was then removed using a combination of O₂ plasma in the RIE tool and acetone baths. The wafer could then be cleaved into 1x0.5 cm chips.

Later etch test chips, as well as the samples used for lasing tests, were patterned with e-beam lithography. This gives the high resolution needed for the coupled disks, and allows for arbitrary computer-aided designs with quick iteration. Wafers or chips were coated with a 3 nm SiO₂ adhesion layer for the resist using ALD, and hydrogen silsesquioxane (HSQ) was deposited on top with spin-coating. This was then exposed with a Vistec EBPG 5200+ machine, and developed. A short RIE removes the adhesion layer, and then the cross-linked HSQ can act as a mask directly.

The patterned designs include long strips of material that can be cleaved such that the cleave line is perpendicular to the strips, and exposes the etched profile to inspection via scanning electron microscopy (SEM). This allows us to precisely inspect the etch rate, selectivity, wall angle, and surface quality. The strips were primarily patterned with optical lithography on bulk InP chips, and the disks and networks with e-beam lithography on bonded material to enable optical confinement and lasing tests.

2.3. Plasma etching

For the dry etching of InP we used the Oxford Instruments Plasmalab 100, an Inductively Coupled Plasma (ICP) Reactive Ion Etching (RIE) tool in the Binnig and Rohrer Nanotechnology Center cleanroom at IBM Research Europe - Zürich. As the cleanroom is used for research purposes, and the tool is used for a variety of different processes, mostly at room temperature, the maximum chamber temperature is 80 °C. This limits the use of common Cl₂ recipes, as the products of In and Cl₂ are

not very volatile and require high temperatures to efficiently desorb from the substrate [21,22].

The etch recipes we concentrate on here can be split into three main categories. First, low temperature chlorine-based chemistries, which aim to overcome the temperature challenge with ion bombardment or plasma heating. After attempting to reproduce results from literature [23–25], we settle on utilising and exploring the parameters of two previously developed recipes [26], similar to ref. [27]. These use Cl₂ and CH₄ as etching agents, and Ar or N₂ for ion bombardment.

The second and third recipes use CH₄ and H₂ as etching agents, which form volatile compounds with In and P respectively at the 80 °C temperature we can reach in our ICP chamber [21]. CH₄ also tends to form polymer deposits that can interfere with the etching [28]. The second recipe we study was previously used for etching of microdisk lasers [17,26,29]. It overcomes the polymerisation issue by etching the material in 2 repeating cycles: 1 min of etching, then 16 s of cleaning the chip with O₂ plasma. This cleans and passivates the surface [30], resulting in highly vertical walls.

The third approach we develop here overcomes the polymerisation by etching at higher powers, with a possible O₂ cleaning step afterwards to remove lingering polymer deposits. To explore the parameters of this approach we have used a Plackett-Burman factorial Design of Experiment (DoE) method, which enables the study of many parameters using comparatively few experimental runs [31]. In our case eight etched samples give insight into the impact of seven parameters.

Post-etch processing can include cleaning with 1:10 diluted phosphoric acid to clean and passivate the etched surface, and capping the chip with a 3 nm layer of Al₂O₃ using atomic layer deposition (ALD). This was done for the final random network and coupled disk sample, but not for the etch test chips.

2.4. Optical investigation

The fabricated microdisk lasers were optically investigated primarily using a picosecond-pulsed supercontinuum laser with a repetition rate of 78 MHz to pump them with light at $\lambda = 750$ nm, that is with photon energies above the InP bandgap. The chips were positioned on a piezoelectric stage, and an objective was used to focus the pump light onto selected devices, and collect the emitted radiation at room temperature. The spot size of our pump laser is 1 μ m in diameter, which is comparable or smaller than all the devices analysed, so we assume all of the pulse power is delivered to the device and use pJ/pulse as the pump energy unit. A similar setup was used for a preliminary test of network lasing, with a higher power laser (at 633 nm, 200 fs pulses, 100 kHz rate) and ability to optically pump larger areas. All lasing results shown were obtained at room temperature.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Chlorine-based etching

Attempts at etching with chlorine-based recipes produced mostly side-walls that were smooth, but not vertical. As shown in Fig. 1, even with some optimisation efforts starting from recipe I, recipe II remained fairly slow and physical, with a low selectivity and wall verticality. Recipe III, which uses argon for bombardment, is more aggressive and high-energy, and therefore faster, but micro-trenching results from its physicality. The higher selectivity is likely a result of the higher proportion of CH₄, and the increased ICP power.

Attempts at further variation, including different gas proportions, temperatures, and pressures resulted in similar or worse performance, with wall slant in the 20° to 25° range. The verticality of the walls is critical for our coupled nanolasers, so the low volatility of InCl₃ in the temperatures we operate at appears to be a major obstacle.

Fig. 1. SEM cross-sections and etch parameters for three ICP etching chemistries primarily based on Cl₂ (labelled with Roman numerals), etched at 20 °C. The selectivity (*Sel.*) compares the etch rate of InP with that of the SiO₂ mask, and *Angle* refers to the side-wall angle from vertical. The ICP and RF (radio frequency) powers correspond to the plasma generation and acceleration powers respectively. The scale of the bar length in each column is consistent in all figures throughout this paper to enable comparison between recipes.

3.2. Methane-based cyclic etching

Cyclic etching results in vertical walls and functional lasing cavities. Fig. 2 presents a representative cross-section and recipe parameters. Etching and cleaning cycles are repeated to achieve the desired etch depth.

Combined with e-beam lithography, this process has proven to lead to very accurate representations of the devices designed in software. We observe a good reproduction of the network patterns on the micron scale (see Fig. 2 d), with waveguide widths and disk dimensions matching the design specification with a few nanometres of precision. The etch also resolves gaps between disk cavities well, with trench widths down to around 35 nm observed.

The cyclic and chemical nature of the etch is visible in the sidewall quality, as shown in Fig. 2 b) and e). Horizontal lines are seen in SEM inspection of the test waveguides where the etching process switched between the etching and cleaning steps. Some general roughness is also

Fig. 2. Etch results and parameters of the cyclic ICP etch recipe primarily based on CH₄. a) An SEM cross-section of a bulk InP etch, 12 cycles used. b) Quality of the InP side-walls before and after a H₃PO₄ bath, with visible horizontal lines corresponding to etch cycles. c) A FIB cross-section of a narrow trench etched in a layer of InP bonded on SiO₂. d) A single lasing network node, showing good transfer of the pattern into the active medium. e) A closer view of a network node, with cyclic etch lines visible along the waveguides.

visible, likely due to the etch relying largely on chemical, somewhat non-uniform desorption of material - both ICP and RF powers are fairly low, so the plasma energy and vertical acceleration are relatively low too. The main disturbance is in this case along the length of the waveguide (see Fig. 2 e), and so should not impact the waveguiding ability too much. The roughness is small enough to not be seen under SEM inspection of both cleaved and focused ion beam (FIB) waveguide cross-sections (Fig. 2 a) and c) respectively). Small deposits of likely condensed In have been seen on the walls in some samples as well, but treating the chip with a diluted H₃PO₄ bath removed these.

3.3. Methane-based continuous etching

Using the same CH₄ etching chemistry as above but running it continuously for a number of minutes results in worsened wall verticality, as seen in Fig. 4 – I. The horizontal roughness of the walls is largely removed, but the isotropic roughness (beyond vertical lines transferred from imperfections in the optical mask) remains, further indicating that it is chemical in nature. The etching is also very slow, and results in polymer deposits visibly settling on the chip, likely impeding etching and optical performance. These can be cleared by adding an O₂ cleaning step after the etch. Optimisation was needed to resolve these issues.

We performed a Plackett-Burman (PB) factorial Design of Experiment (DoE) study to roughly establish the influence of various etching parameters on the etch rate, selectivity, and wall angle. The parameters varied were the ICP and RF powers, chamber pressure, gas flow of CH₄, H₂, and Ar, and whether the sample was ‘clamped’ – glued to the carrier wafer, with He flow keeping the carrier thermally coupled to the ICP machine’s chuck and thus more steady at the set chamber temperature. 8 etch runs were performed on chips prepared with e-beam lithography, with parameter values determined by a PB matrix. The etched chips were cleaved, and etch quality assessed under SEM inspection. The resulting etch properties can then be selectively averaged to assess the mean impact of a property value changing from low to high.

The changes due the various parameters, and the definitions of ‘low’

Fig. 3. An overview of the Design of Experiment exploration of continuous CH₄-based etching. The first table shows the high and low values of the 7 parameters tested, and a-d) show the average impact of going from low to high values of these parameters for four figures of merit (illustrated in the inset drawing). Blue bars indicate the desirable condition: lower angle, higher etch rate, etc. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

and ‘high’ for each parameter, are shown in Fig. 3. The data gives some indication of the direction in which optimisation should go. We observe that higher ICP and RF powers lead to smooth side walls (compare Fig. 4 – I and II), but going too high can be detrimental to the wall angle, and lead to uneven etching of the bulk InP, producing bulk surface roughness (this is less critical for bonded layers). CH₄ is observed to play a key role in material removal, compared with the lesser impact of H₂ variation. A need for informed decisions in optimisation is illustrated as well – for example, we can opt for a lower etch rate if it leads to better wall angles.

Notably, the full impact of interactions *between* the parameters is not accounted for in a PB study with 8 experimental runs. Fig. 4 – II-IV show one of the DoE etches, and two other attempts that explore other corners of the parameter space. For example, it appears that lowering H₂ flow too much at higher pressures can lead to etches that are more isotropic and produce small overhangs (Fig. 4 – III). Lower pressures seem to work reasonably well with higher powers, producing one of the lower wall angles seen (Fig. 4 – IV). This shows that after identifying the core parameters in the study above, it’s possible to further tease out parameter relationships through experimentation or different DoE methodologies with fewer parameters.

3.4. Lasing verification

We fabricated a test design that included circular and hexagonal disk cavities out of a bonded layer of 140 nm InP. The disks of various sizes support whispering gallery modes at different wavelengths. An example of a lasing mode is shown in Fig. 5 a). The bulk photoluminescence (PL) spectrum of InP is broad, and above it we see a narrower peak arising out of a wider amplified stimulated emission resonance. We can fit and subtract the bulk PL of InP around the peak to obtain the intensity of just the resonant emission, which is shown in b). As the resonance narrows to a peak and its intensity rapidly grows, a characteristic onset is seen in the intensity curve. This narrowing, intensity onset, and fringes observed in the far field emission showing coherent emission (see the Fig. 5 b) inset) are signs of lasing [29,32], and fitting to the intensity data above the kink lets us extract the lasing threshold. The threshold is a function of cavity quality, but also the lasing wavelength (through distance from the band gap) and the amount of gain medium (the size of the device). If a single cavity supports multiple modes within the gain spectrum, their thresholds can also be impacted by the modes competing with each other for gain [33]. Overall trends between samples can be compared still.

The four samples discussed here were fabricated with the cyclic CH₄ recipe, a variant of a continuous CH₄ recipe close to optimal according to the DoE study, and variants I and III of the Cl₂ recipes from Fig. 1. The buried oxide layer was 2 μm. Compared to etching bulk material, the same recipes seem to etch bonded InP slightly slower, and with wall

angles slightly larger, but the difference is not major, so we employ the same chemistry with etch times increased to compensate, and to make sure small trenches are resolved well.

Fig. 5 c) shows a comparison of the lasing thresholds extracted out of circular disk lasers on the four samples. Fig. 5 c) – I shows the performance of the cyclic CH₄ etch, with most devices at thresholds in the 0.72 pJ/pulse to 3.0 pJ/pulse range, comparable or lower than those seen from etched and TASE-grown InP hexagons in a previous study, which were reported in the 1.81 pJ/pulse to 1.93 pJ/pulse range [17].

The continuous CH₄ etch devices shown in Fig. 5 c) – II initially perform worse, but a further O₂ plasma clean brings the sample nearer to the baseline of the cyclic devices. This highlights both that polymer deposits may not be entirely removed with higher power etching, and the value of lasing tests for highlighting fabrication issues in our application.

Continuous Cl₂ etches are shown in Fig. 5 c) – III, achieving performance comparable to cyclic etching. This highlights that smooth cavities can lead to good lasing performance, despite the slanted walls impeding the total internal reflection necessary to support whispering gallery modes. The angles of the cavity walls still make the use of this chemistry difficult for coupled cavity studies, where narrow trenches are necessary.

3.5. Complex nanophotonic lasing

A rudimentary study of coupled behaviour from two coupled disk cavities with a diameter of 2 μm each and a designed gap of roughly 25 nm between them is shown in Fig. 5 d). The 1 μm diameter pump laser spot is swept across the two devices, effectively changing the gain ratio between them. As predicted by coupled mode theory [12], the two modes interact and evolve in wavelength as the gain ratio changes, indicating that the fabricated devices are indeed coupled.

Fig. 5 e) shows the emission spectrum from a small area of a lasing network consisting of 350 nm-wide waveguides etched into a 120 nm layer of InP. Upon optical pumping of an inner area (20 μm in diameter) of the network, resonant modes arise from the bulk photoluminescence above a pump power threshold. As only few network links are pumped, lasing is likely achieved from Fabry-Perot modes that are confined in the waveguides and coupled through scattering at the network’s nodes. The occurrence of lasing from only a few links indicates good waveguiding and low scattering losses, and highlights etching of bonded III-V semiconductors as a promising platform for network lasing studies [9,10].

4. Conclusion

Top down fabrication is well-suited for our complex nanophotonic devices. We demonstrate that it can reproduce the computer-designed structures we desire with good accuracy, and high quality cavities and waveguides. It is capable of producing both narrow gaps for the coupled lasers, and good-quality waveguides for lasing networks – with preliminary results of lasing from both kinds of devices.

We explored ICP RIE etching of InP at temperatures up to 80 °C, evaluating results from previously published methods, and developing paths forward for potentially even better-performing etched cavities with smoother side-walls, including through a Design of Experiment study. We also presented the use of cavity lasing as a proxy for fabrication fidelity, using it to inform optimisation and evaluate processes, highlighting the importance of cavity wall smoothness and post-etch O₂ cleaning for CH₄ chemistries.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

Jakub Dranczewski reports financial support was provided by EU ITN EID project CORAL (GA no. 859841). Anna Fischer reports financial

Fig. 4. Etch results and parameters of four coupled ICP etch recipes primarily based on CH₄. I illustrates the rough surface at low powers, II is one etch from the DoE study, III shows a slight overhang at high powers and H₂ flow, and IV shows how lower pressures can lead to low wall angles.

Fig. 5. Lasing from our fabricated devices. a) A spectrum of a lasing peak emerging from the bulk photoluminescence (PL) of a hexagonal InP disk, 0.7 μm in radius. One spectrum is highlighted in orange – there, a narrow peak emerges from a cavity resonance on top of the bulk PL (dashed fit line). As the power rises, this peak dominates the bulk PL. b) Subtracting a fit of the bulk PL and integrating the remaining signal, we can obtain the intensity of resonant emission plus lasing as a function of pump power. Fitting above the inflection point lets us extract the lasing threshold. The inset shows the far field emission of a disc device above this threshold, demonstrating fringes (partially highlighted orange) characteristic of coherent emission. c) Comparison of the lasing threshold measured for circular disks on chips etched with different chemistries. The threshold is a function of wavelength (distance of the mode from the band gap), and a proxy for cavity quality. Some devices support two lasing modes within a single cavity – in that case the pair of modes is linked by a line on the plot. The sizes of the points correspond to the radius of the measured device. d) Evolution of lasing modes from two coupled disks with a radius of 1 μm . By sweeping the pump laser spot across the devices, we change the ratio of gain for the two, leading to coupled mode evolution. e) Spectrum resulting from pumping a small area of a lasing network (drawing of the network shown in inset, with the illuminated area in grey and pumped waveguides in black), with modes emerging as the pump power increases.

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Data availability

The data used is available in the Zenodo repository: 10.5281/zenodo.7515880

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